

Yield potential

Correlation and path analysis of rice grain yield under alkali stress conditions

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We studied direct and indirect associations of yield components with grain yield in 27 short-duration rice genotypes to identify suitable criteria for effective selection of genotypes under alkaline stress condition.

The experiment was laid out at CRS in a randomized block design during 1993 wet season (rabi) with three replications. The soil was clay loam with pH 8.6, EC

1.4 dS/m, and 18% exchangeable Na. The soil had low N (109 kg), low P (10.8 kg), and high K (672 kg). The crop received 125-50-50 kg NPK/ha during the season. We transplanted 25-d-old rice seedlings at 20- × 10-cm spacing in 2- × 3-m plots. The genotypes had 105-115 d durations and grain yield varied from 1.7 to 6.0 t/ha.

Grain yield was positively and significantly correlated with panicle length ($r = 0.578$), grains per panicle ($r = 0.547$), 100-grain weight ($r = 0.401$), dry matter production ($r = 0.901$), and straw yield ($r = 0.752$) (see table). Straw yield was positively and significantly correlated with plant height ($r = 0.523$), panicle length ($r = 0.698$), grains per panicle ($r = 0.544$), and dry matter production ($r = 0.858$). Dry matter production was significantly and

positively correlated with plant height ($r = 0.44$), panicle length ($r = 0.692$), grains per panicle ($r = 0.600$), 100-grain weight ($r = 0.410$), and root weight ($r = 0.378$).

Path analysis studies indicated that dry matter production had a high direct effect on grain yield (see table). Productive tillers per plant and grains per panicle had low direct effects. For the other traits, the effect was negative. Although panicle length, 100-grain weight, and straw yield had a positive and significant correlation with grain yield, they did not exhibit direct effect on grain yield. These characters had an indirect effect on grain yield, mainly through dry matter production.

Dry matter production seems to be the most reliable character for effective selection of genotypes under alkali stress conditions. ■

Coefficients of correlation and path analysis^a showing direct and indirect effects of yield components on grain yield under alkali stress condition. Srivilliputtur, India. 1993.

Variable		Plant height	Panicle length	Productive tillers/plant	Grains/panicle	100-grain weight	Root weight	Dry matter production	Straw yield	Grain yield
Panicle height	rg ^b	-	0.574**	-0.303	0.306	0.184	0.255	0.440*	0.523**	0.263
	P ^c	<u>-0.059</u>	-0.014	-0.029	0.015	-0.006	-0.072	0.545	-0.118	-
Panicle length	rg	-	-	-0.089	0.647**	0.139	0.298	0.692**	0.698**	0.578**
	P	-0.034	<u>-0.024</u>	-0.009	0.032	-0.005	-0.084	0.857	-0.157	-
Productive tillers/plant	rg	-	-	-	0.024	-0.215	0.180	-0.137	-0.018	-0.091
	P	0.018	0.002	<u>0.097</u>	0.001	0.007	-0.051	-0.169	0.004	-
Grains/panicle	rg	-	-	-	-	-0.188	0.352	0.600**	0.544**	0.547**
	P	-0.018	-0.016	0.002	<u>0.050</u>	0.006	-0.099	0.743	-0.122	-
100-grain weight	rg	-	-	-	-	-	-0.127	0.410*	0.291	0.401*
	P	-0.011	-0.003	-0.021	-0.010	<u>-0.032</u>	0.036	0.508	-0.066	-
Root weight	rg	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.378*	0.193	0.161
	P	-0.015	-0.007	0.017	0.018	0.004	<u>-0.281</u>	0.469	-0.043	-
Dry matter production	rg	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.858**	0.901*
	P	-0.026	-0.017	-0.013	0.030	-0.013	-0.106	<u>1.239</u>	-0.193	-
Straw yield	rg	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.752**
	P	-0.031	-0.017	-0.002	0.027	-0.009	-0.054	1.062	<u>-0.225</u>	-

^a Residual effect = 0.35; underlined figures denote direct effects. * and ** = significant at the 5 and 1% level, respectively. ^b rg = genotypic correlation coefficient. ^c P = path coefficient.

Grain quality

Milling characters of raw and parboiled popular rice cultivars

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More than half of the rice consumed in India is parboiled; in Tamil Nadu State it exceeds 85%. Raw and parboiled rices have different qualities. We investigated the differences in some milling characters between raw and parboiled rices in 15 popular cultivars.

Nine short-duration (10.5- 120 d) cultivars were grown in 1992 kuruvai

season (Jun-Jul sowings) and six medium-duration (125-140 d) cultivars in 1992 thaladi season (Sep-Oct sowings). A recommended package of practices was followed for a transplanted lowland crop. Seeds were collected from replicated trials, cleaned, and dried to 14% moisture content. Samples were drawn 1 mo after harvest. One half was